

The quartz and quartzite lithotheque of the CENIEH: A wide variety of lithic raw materials

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1. Introduction and materials

The following report tries to summarise the most relevant features to understand the report we have conducted for the *Centro Nacional de Investigación en Evolución Humana* CENIEH, Burgos.

The material here analysed consists on 73 samples from the CENIEH. Due to in course research, two of them, are not shown in this report, but will be available in the future. This material came from different previous projects that are here summarised:

Projects	Quantity of sample
Litho.Aranbaltza	1
Litho.Arlanpe	1
Litho.Arlanzón	22
Litho.CuestaBajada	7
Litho.Hornos	1
Litho.Miño	8
Litho.NaiborSoilNdogo	2
Litho.Olduvai	1
Litho.Olmos de Atapuerca	19
Litho.PeñaMiel	1
Litho.PinedadelaSierra	3
Litho.TercerNaibor	2
Litho.Tormes	1
Litho.Utrillas	2
Litho.?	2

There is a high variability of material here analysed, and, despite most of it is what archaeologist name as quartzite, there are sandstones and quartz, also a limestone. We have classified them according to their petrogenesis, that is, how and under which condition, they have been created.

2. Methodology

The methodology applied employs a multi-scalar strategy, that put together stereoscopic observations of inner and cortical areas of the stones and thin section petrography.

2.1. Thin section petrography

Thin section petrography adhered to the methodology proposed by Prieto et al. (Prieto et al., 2019). We classified the **homogeneity of the thin section** as a) *very homogeneous*, b) *homogeneous*, c) *heterogeneous*, and d) *zoned* (in case the heterogeneity is made by particular areas). The joints presented were also quantified depending of the different planes they were organised (one, two or three joint planes). We characterised **the texture**, distinguishing between a) *clastic texture with matrix or cement (matrix supported texture)*, b) *clastic grained texture*, c) *foam or mortar texture*, d) *porphyroblastic texture*, e) *nematoblastic texture*, and *interlocking quartz grains* (Figure 1). The **packing** of each section was characterised as a) *floating*, b) *punctual*, c) *tangential*, d) *complete*, or e) *saturated* (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Microphotographs of six textures characterised in thin section in this report. A) The sample CENIEH.199 exhibits clastic texture with matrix or cement (matrix supported texture). B) The sample CENIEH.F.017 exhibits classic grained texture. C) The sample CENIEH.216 exhibits foam texture. D) The sample CENIEH.F.010 has porphyroblastic texture. E) The sample CENIEH.182 exhibits nematoblastic texture. Finally, the sample CENIEH.222 is a quartz with grains interlocking and creating saturated and straight contacts between grains.

Figure 2. Microphotographs of five quartzite thin section at different magnification attending to the packing criteria. From left to right A) floating (CENIEH.032), B) punctual (CENIEH.031), C)

tangential (CENIEH.039), complete (CENIEH.198) and saturated (CENIEH.176). From left to right CENIEH.032, CENIEH.031, CENIEH.F.023, CENIEH.198 and CENIEH.175.

The **sorting of quartz grains** is also classified following the Folk classification (Folk, 1974) as a) *very poorly sorted*, b) *poorly sorted*, c) *moderated sorted*, d) *well sorted* or *very well sorted*. We have also classified the thin section having in mind **the orientation of the particles**, describing them as a) *sedimentary stratification*, b) *metamorphic foliation*, c) *bidirectional foliation* or d) *through modulating foliation* (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Microscopic pictures with different quartz grain orientation identified in thin sections. A) Non oriented quartz grains particle from the sample CENIEH.039. B) Sedimentary oriented quartz grains from the sample CENIEH.037. C) One-way foliation structure from the sample CENIEH.176. D) Bidirectional foliation on the sample CENIEH.228.

We have characterised and quantified **up to three different types of quartz grains features** using the following criteria: a) *detritic quartz grains* (Figures 4.A), b) *Weathered quartz grains* (Figures 4.B), c) *Polycrystalline quartz grains* (Figures 4.C), d) *quartz grains with syntaxial overgrowth* (Figures 4.D), e) *concave-convex quartz grain limits* (Figures 4.E), f) *undulate extinction quartz grains* (Figures 4.F), g) *saturated or stylolitic quartz grains* (Figures 5.A), g) *Böhm lamellae* (Figure 5.B), f) *recrystallised quartz grains* (Figure 5.C), h) *quartz grains forming 120° triple points (polygonal)* (Figure 5.D), k) *abnormal coarse quartz grain* (Figure 5.E), and l) *straight quartz grain limits*

(Figure 5.F). These features were described in (Favreau et al., 2020; Hirth & Tullis, 1992; Howard, 2000; Prieto et al., 2019; Skolnick, 1965; Soto et al., 2020; Tarriño et al., 2023; Wilson, 1973). Each of the grain or feature category described was quantified. If two or three features are part of the same grains, they share the same percentage. If not, they are quartz grains features that can appear on the same thin section. The **morphology** and **size** is described following (Folk, 1974; Wentworth, 1922).

Figure 4. Microscopic pictures of quartz grain features identified in thin sections. A) Detrital quartz grains from the sample CENIEH.F.016. B) Quartz grains with weathered borders from the sample CENIEH.031. C) Two polycrystalline quartz grains on the sample CENIEH.031. The upper one is probably a flint fragment and the one on the right part of the image is an old quartzite s.s.. D) Quartz grain with syntaxial overgrowths. They creates concavo-convex limits with surrounded quartz grains. E) Concave-convex quartz grain limits that are turning toward a saturated limits; F) Quartz grains with undulate extinction from the sample CENIEH.F.011.

Figure 5. Microscopic pictures of quartz grain features identified in thin sections. A) Saturated quartz grains from the sample CENIEH.197. B) Böhm lamellae on quartz grains from the sample CENIEH.037 (at the bottom of the image). C) Recrystallised (small in size) quartz grains on the sample CENIEH.037 (also old, big and highly deformed quartz grains). D) Polygonised quartz grains with 120° triple joints from the sample CENIEH.026. E) abnormal coarse quartz grain; F) Quartz grains with straight (also few saturated) limits from the sample CENIEH.023.

The acquired data facilitated the classification of each section into the seven **petrogenetic types** proposed by previous research in the Cantabrian Region (Prieto et al., 2019): *clastic fabric with Matrix or non-quartz cement quartz Arenite (MA)*, *Clastic Quartz arenite (CA)*, *syntaxially Overgrown Orthoquartzite (OO)*, *Sutured grain Orthoquartzite (SO)*, *Bulging recrystallized Quartzite (BQ)*, *subgrain Rotation recrystallized Quartzite (RQ)*, and *grain boundary Migration recrystallized Quartzite (MQ)*. It is important to mention that we have characterised another two types, described in the bibliography, but that were not described in other geoarchaeological studies in the Iberian Peninsula. They are the *Polygonal grains recrystallised Quartzite (PQ)* and the *Abnormal Coarsing Grain Recrystallised Quartzite (AQ)*. According to (Howard, 2000, 2005; Skolnick, 1965; Wilson, 1973), the first type is characterised by a mosaic of quartz grains creating 120° triple points. They are recrystallised grains, generally with well-developed deformation structures such as deformation bands and Bohm lamellae. The

second type, AQ, is characterised by the presence of recrystallised quartz grains. Few of them are abnormally coarse when they are compared with other recrystallised quartz grains. It was possible also to observe at certain orientations these grains seem to be composed of different grains that were put together due to the high pressure. The presence of original grains in both types is minimal or simply inexistence and it is possible to observe different petrogenetic types on the same thin section. This is probably the reflection of different deformation bands or the differential affection of the same metamorphic effect on different original petrooliths. In these cases, quartzites were assigned to the higher metamorphic degree petrogenetic type.

Finally, we described **the non-quartz mineral** presented on the thin section following (Adams et al., 1988; Gil Crespo, 2009; MacKenzie & Adams, 1997; Yardley et al., 1990). **The presence of matrix and/or cement** have also been mineralogically described and **quantified** using the following categories: <5%, 5-20% and >20%.

2.2. Stereomicroscopy and *de visu* petrographic characterisation

Non-cortical surface characterization involved stereoscope microscopy, following the protocol established by Prieto et al. (Prieto et al., 2020, 2021). Four scales of observation were applied, ranging from naked-eye description to x250 magnification using the Dino-Lite digital microscope and stereomicroscopes. Photomicrographs were captured, and features were used to classify quartzites into petrogenetic types, determining grain-size mean value and non-quartz minerals. Most of the pieces were photographed in a flat position to X50 and X250 magnification to create a library of reference pictures. We preferentially used Dino-Lite model AD7013MZT with polarized light to eliminate most of the surface lustre. The microscope was handled with the MS35B vertical stand. We used the software Dino-Capture 2.0. The stereomicroscope used was the Nikon SMZ800, with up to X120 magnification. The association of most features classified each quartzite into the petrogenetic types, but also characterised the grain-size mean value and the non-quartz minerals.

The colour of inner part of the quartzites is characterised by nine basic colour options. If more than one is referred, it is because there are both colour on the sample or the intersection of two or more are assigned.

We qualitatively systematised **lustre** to the naked eye on the surface of quartzites in four categories: a) *no lustre*, b) *low lustre*, c) *medium lustre* and d) *high lustre*. **Density of surface micro-cracks/chips** in the surface of quartzite to naked eye. These areas are characterised as lighter and sparkling elements with scale morphology that appears on the surface of quartzites. We systematised their presence using the following criteria: a) *absence*, b) *small*, c) *medium* or d) *high presence* of micro-cracks (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Surface micro-cracks presented in the Sample CENIEH.039. To the naked eye, white, irregular and lighter superficial areas are identified. At X 20, X 50 and X 250 magnification surface microcracks are also present and recognised by similar features.

We distinguished five different types of **packing in hand specimens** according to the categories used for thin section and the following criteria: a) *Floating*, if the quartz grains are separated one from each other by matrix or cement. b) *Punctual or isolated*, when the quartz grains are one near another and the contacts between them are restricted to single points. At ranges between x 50 and x 250, the grains are closer to each other, but contacts are very small or absent. c) *Tangential*, in case the grains are joined together, but cement is still present. At X 50–X 250 magnifications, the cement is restricted to a thin layer between the limits of the quartz grains. d) *Complete*, where there is a very small content of cement or matrix and the grains create an almost complete texture. Matrix or cement is almost absent, limited to few accumulations in small confined areas between grains. They are delimited by very weak, fine and straight contours. e) *Suturated*, when the limits between grains generate a complete and deformed texture. Matrix or cement is restricted to small points on quartz limits, as in the previous packing type (Figure7).

Figure 7. Microphotographs of the surface of five different archaeological quartzites at 250x magnification attending to the packing criteria. From left to right floating, punctual, tangential, complete and saturated. From left to right CENIEH.032, CENIEH.031, CENIEH.F.023, CENIEH.198 and CENIEH.175.

We distinguished six different **types of texture**, not only attending to the perception of the surface relief or the feel (touch) of the quartzite surface, but also using criteria observable by stereomicroscope. Texture categories are the following: *a) Saccharoidal texture* is defined by the generalised presence of matrix or a carbonate cement on the surface of the samples. The touch is granular and sandy and it is usually heterogeneously coloured to the naked eye. At low magnification, slopes and rough relief are appreciated. At middle magnification, it is possible to observe the presence of isolated to tangential quartz grains surrounded by large amounts of matrix and secondary diagenetic cement, creating a rough relief. Some quartz grains can sparkle, but the lustre is not homogeneously distributed. At high magnification, quartz grains tend to be isolated and, again surrounded by matrix, generally as the sum of small specks that cover the surface of quartz and other mineral grains. *b) Granular texture* is defined by a clear granular touch on the surface of the sample. The quantity of matrix or cement is reduced and its presence is restricted to small areas or the surroundings of the edges of the grains. To the naked eye, it generally shows a heterogeneous colour distribution. At low magnification, softly rough to flat relief is appreciated. At middle magnification, it is possible to recognise quartz grains and some of them can sparkle, but lustre is not homogenous. At high magnification, grains of these rocks are also recognisable and small quantities of cement or matrix (mainly formed by the sum of small specks) fill the small empty areas between quartz grains. *c) Compact and grainy texture* is defined by the presence of a very soft granulated touch on the surface of the sample. There is no presence of matrix or cement. To the naked eye, the colour is more homogeneous and micro-cracks are recognisable. At low magnification, the relief is gentler than that in the previous texture and some of the surfaces show successive planes of squamous surfaces. At middle magnification, most of the grains are still recognisable, especially the lighter grains which show clear and curved outlines, although some parts of them cannot be appreciated. In a same way, at high magnification, grains are recognisable, especially those with thicker, brighter and curved outlines. Other grains or parts of the outlines are vague or diffused. The previously commented lighter grains are visible.

Figure 8. Microphotograph of the surface of three quartzites. On the left, X 50 magnification picture and, on the right, X 250 magnification one. From top to bottom, Saccharoidal texture (CENIEH.152); granular texture (CENIEH.F.035); and, compact and grainy texture (CENIEH.F.009).

d) *Fine and grainy texture* is defined by a smooth touch and a moderate lustre. In general, grains are difficult to observe completely. Although the touch is fine, small rough areas could be observed, mainly generated by the presence of secondary ferruginous, siliceous or carbonate precipitates or by the presence of joints. To the naked eye, colour is relatively homogeneous, except in micro-cracks, which are generally brighter. At low magnification, the relief is soft without roughness, although some surfaces of the quartzite show squamous surfaces. At middle magnifications, grains are hardly recognisable and there is a thin and bright lustre covering the surface of the rock. At high magnification, grains are almost unrecognisable and only some outlines can be appreciated. Small specks are visible on the outlines of the quartz grains and they seem to be on the same level as the rest of the surface, covered by the previously mentioned thin and bright lustre. e) *Fine texture* is defined by a really smooth touch and a shiny/brilliant lustre. In general, grains cannot be observed and only some small relicts from their outlines are seen. The touch is very fine and, as in the previous texture, some areas can be rougher due to cement precipitations. To the naked eye, colour is homogenous and shows a high lustre. Micro-cracks are much more limited than those in

the previous texture, although they are present. At low magnification, the relief is very soft and no rugosity is observed; neither is there a large quantity of squamous surfaces, which are reduced to very small areas. At middle magnification, no grains are recognisable and only small specks are visible. Thin and bright lustre is observed and it clearly covers the entire surface of the quartzite. At high magnification, no grain is observed and only small specks or associations of them are recognised on the surface, reduced to small areas. *f) Soapy texture* is quite similar to the preceding one. The touch is soapy, even smoother than that in the previous texture, and no grains are observed. To the naked eye, colour is really homogeneous, very bright, and microcracks are limited. At low magnification, the relief is plain and soft and there is almost no plain squamous surface. At middle magnifications, no grains are recognisable and neither are the small specks appreciated in the preceding texture. Previous thin and bright lustre is extended onto the entire surface of the quartzite. At high magnifications, only a few grains are recognisable, not by the outlines but by a small, thin and almost unrecognisable bulging that creates a wavy micro-relief. Hardly any small specks are appreciated.

Figure 9. Microphotograph of the surface of three quartzite pieces taken at X 50 magnification (left) and at X 250 magnification (right). From top to bottom, fine and grainy texture (CENIEH.165); fine texture (CENIEH.F.035); and soapy texture (CENIEH.F.216)

Quartz grain features were determined by applying morphological features of the border of the quartz grains. We reduced the variability of each quartzite to the two

prevailing categories. These were: a) *Quartz grains with flat and angular limits*. b) *Quartz grains with flat and rounded limits*. c) *Quartz grains with ruffled and irregular limits generated by the effect of matrix or cement*. d) *Quartz grains with appearance of regrowth of quartz syntaxial cement*, recognisable by the partial or complete dual grain outline that creates a lighter, glossy and curved space between both lines, generally in concavo-convex lines between grains. e) *Quartz grains with ruffled, irregular and thin limits and surfaces with flat relief*. f) *Quartz grains with no boundaries detected*, where the limits are reduced to small alignments of specks or small saturated lines.

In addition to the proper characterisation of the quartzites using aforementioned criteria (useful for future researcher in the Cenieh lithotheque), all these data were used to assign every quartzite here analysed following scheme (Figure X). It is important to mention that the two new types characterised though thin section were not included here because of the small quantity of stones characterised as Polygonal grains recrystallised Quartzite (PQ) -only present in alternation of quartzite types together with PQ- and the Abnormal coarsing grain recrystallised quartzite (AQ). Moreover, features such as soapy textures and no grain detections are evident in the three samples characterised. The presence of few grains (similar to those of quartz), could be the abnormally growth grains.

We determined **mean grain size** using X 50 and X 250 magnifications, obtaining the approximate measurement of the secondary axis of the particles. The measurement was performed with the measuring mode provided by the software Dino-Capture 2.0. In general, the number of measured grains per sample is higher than 20. So we used three categories, based on the Udden-Wentworth scale (Wentworth, 1922) and modified for their application to quartz grains according to the conclusion reached by Prieto et al. 2019: (a) *Coarse quartz grain size*, used for quartzites containing quartz grains bigger than fine sand (> 0.25 mm); (b) *medium quartz grain size*, used for quartz grains between coarse silt and fine sand (0.062 to 0.25 mm); and (c) *fine quartz grain size*, used for quartzites with grains smaller than coarse silt (< 0.062). For heterogeneous samples, the biggest grain determined was assigned as the size of the quartzite. We completed the qualitative analysis of quartz grains by describing their **sorting degree** using the following categories: a) *homogeneous*, b) *bimodal* or c) *heterogeneous quartz grain* according to the size distribution.

We also noted the **presence of bedding planes** on the surface of quartzites, both to the naked eye and using low magnification, according to the following criteria: a) *absence of bedding*, b) *non-clear bedding* and c) *clear bedding*. Finally, we tried to recognize **foliation** features on at least one surface of the sample, although this is not an easy task in hand specimens of highly compact quartzites.

Fig. 10. Microphotograph of the surface of two quartzite pieces at X 50 and X 250 magnifications. On the left side, the sample CENIEH.022 exhibits clear bedding of the surface with grains preferentially oriented and silica matrix filling the empty space between them. No grain is deformed. On the right side, the sample CENIEH.011 shows clear foliation. It is easy to distinguish schistosity from bedding owing to the modification of quartz grains in the former, while in the latter no modification of quartz grains is observable (both observations at X 250 magnification).

In addition to quartz, archaeological quartzites contain **other minerals** in very small proportions. Up to three of the most representative minor minerals were identified in every sample. The observed minerals are the following: as primary phases a) *white mica*, b) *feldspars*, c) *pyrite* and d) *undetermined black minerals*, and as alteration phases e) *Iron* and d) *Manganese oxides*.

Figure 11. Microphotograph of the surface of six quartzite: a) X 250 magnification: orange/red irregular iron oxides at the sample CENIEH.018. b) X 20 magnification: black and irregular manganese oxides at the sample CENIEH.031. c) X 250 magnification: two black, plain and subrounded undetermined heavy minerals at the sample CENIEH.023. d) X 50 magnification: very small, black, plain and angular pyrites at the sample CENIEH.0.38. e) X 50 small, white and bright exfoliating feldspars at the sample CENIEH.221. f) X 250 magnification: small, white and bright mica with changeable structures at the sample CENIEH.175.

Finally, the cortical areas were characterized following the proposal by Fernandes *et al.* (2007) and Fernandes and Raynal (2006), linking these data to specific raw material sources. These surfaces were characterised using the following criteria: **Touch**, referring to a) *coarse grained*, b) *fine grained*, c) *fine* and d) *soapy texture*. We also characterise the **presence of inclusions** on them, being a) *iron* or b) *manganese oxides*, c) *carbonates* or d) *silica precipitations*. We also characterise the presence of **specific features** such as a) *the presence of small animals* (lithophagous), b) *vegetal imprints* or c) *vacuoles*. We characterise the presence of **impact cracks**, trying to classify them to unveils if they derived from a) *fluvial* or b) *gravitational* processes. **The presence of joints** is also described and quantified by its organisation a) *unidirectional*, b) *bidirectional* and c) *tridirectional*. Of course, **Colour of these surfaces** is characterised by nine basic colour options. If more than one is referred, it is because there are both colour on the sample or the intersection of two or more are assigned.

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